

Title: Open Blockchain Platform : OpenchainGlobal.

SUB TITLE : From community to enterprise, from platform to various application.

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INTRODUCTION:

Application & use of cases of blockchain.

Open blockchain platform supports

- multi platforms

. Multichain,

Ethereum,

Hyperledger

- multi programming languages.

. Java,

Golang,

Python,

PHP -

Multifields

.

general

finance

& advanced

Fintech

. P2P

Crowdfunding.

Cryptocurrency /

ICO

Real estate,

Used

. Big data, Cloud computing, AI

car

sales

Open blockchain platform supports

-multi platforms

Multichain, Ethereum, Hyperledger